

Floral characters of CMS and maintainer lines in hybrid rice

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We screened five male sterile lines and their maintainers for pistil and stamen length during 1986 wet season (kharif). Fifty spikelets/line were measured.

Among the A lines, IR46830A had the longest pistil, V41A the shortest. Among B lines, Zhen Shan 97B had the longest stamen, IR54752B the shortest. V20A and Zhen Shan 97B had the longest filament (see table).

The long Zhen Shan 97B stamen, prominently protruding from the gap

Expression of floral characters in A, B, and R lines of hybrid rice.

Line	Stamen (mm)				Pistil (mm)			
	Filament length	Anther length	Anther breadth	Stamen length	Ovary length	Style length	Stigma length	Pistil length
V20A	2.75	2.78	0.32	5.53	0.801	0.840	1.280	2.921
V20B	3.59	2.39	0.50	5.98	0.944	1.024	1.240	3.208
V41A	2.12	2.03	0.37	4.15	0.704	0.640	0.816	2.160
V41B	3.05	2.08	0.41	5.13	0.816	0.832	0.936	2.584
Zhen Shan 97A	2.99	2.12	0.48	5.11	0.576	0.872	1.112	2.560
Zhen Shan 97B	3.48	2.57	0.48	6.05	0.728	0.984	0.992	2.704
IR46830A	2.65	2.13	0.38	4.78	1.104	0.881	1.080	3.065
IR46830B	3.30	2.21	0.42	5.51	1.267	1.216	1.320	3.803
IR54752A	1.33	1.68	0.34	3.01	0.760	0.720	0.826	2.306
IR54752B	1.70	1.73	0.36	3.43	0.770	0.760	0.880	2.410
SE	0.44	0.22	0.09	0.45	0.21	0.17	0.17	0.28

between lemma and palea, facilitated easy transfer of pollen to the stigma of corresponding A lines in the adjoining row.

In general, all the male sterile (A) lines had smaller stamens and pistils than their respective maintainers. □

Effect of row ratio and leaf clipping on MR365A outcrossing and seed yield

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We evaluated the effect of row ratio and leaf clipping on outcrossing rate and seed yield of MR365A (a CMS line developed at IRRI) during 1984-85 wet

season, in a split-plot design with three replications. Seedlings (21 d) were transplanted at 1 seedling/hill with 20 × 20-cm spacing.

Among the three male-to-female ratios tested, seed yields of 1B:4A and 1B:2A were significantly higher than that of 2B:4A (Table 1). Seed set was not significantly different among the ratios.

Leaf clipping increased seed set, but significantly reduced grains/panicle,

perhaps because of lower panicle exertion. Filled grains/panicle and seed yield/m² were not affected by leaf clipping (Table 2). There was no interaction between row ratio and leaf clipping. □

Table 1. Effect of row ratio on seed yield, seed set, number of grains, and number of filled grains of MR365A.

Row ratio	Seed yield (g/m ²)	Seed set/panicle (%)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)
2B:4A	67.6 b	23.76 a	94.16 b	22.28 b
1B:4A	85.4 a	22.82 a	98.96 ab	22.33 b
1B:2A	88.5 a	23.41 a	107.32 a	24.95 a
CV (%)	6.5	17.29	7.81	15.04

Table 2. Effect of leaf clipping on seed yield, seed set, number of grains, and number of filled grains of MR365A.

Leaf clipping	Seed yield (g/m ²)	Seed set/panicle (%)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)
Clipped	83.21 a	25.14 a	92.19 b	23.26 a
Uncropped	77.75 a	21.52 b	108.10 a	23.12 a
CV (%)	15.96	10.15	8.69	12.55

Somatic embryogenesis in rice cultivar IR50

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Initiation and development of embryos from somatic tissues in rice have been achieved by culturing seed-derived callus of IR50. Mature dehulled seeds were inoculated on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium with varying concentrations of 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4-D) and kinetin (see table). Medium pH was adjusted to 5.8. The cultures were kept in light for 14 h daylength at 24 ± 2 °C.

Calli were initiated from the hypocotyls of the seedlings within 15 d after inoculation. Callus induction increased with increasing concentrations of 2, 4-D to 2 mg/liter. Higher concentrations inhibited callus growth.